

Kidney Disease Related Death in Working Age Group Over a Ten-Year Period at One Selected Public Hospital in Myanmar: A Retrospective Descriptive Study

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: The prevalence of non-communicable disease is increasing world-wide; chronic kidney disease is one of them. The burden of kidney disease related mortality in working age group was not reported from Myanmar.

Methods: A hospital based retrospective descriptive study was conducted in one selected public hospital in Yangon, Myanmar. The design focused on analyzing data from brought-in-deaths (BID) and hospital admission deaths (HAD) among the working age group (18-62 years) over a 10-year period; January 1, 2015 to December 31, 2024. All cases underwent postmortem examination done by a forensic surgeon for BID cases and a pathologist for HAD cases. And the cause of death was verified.

Results: A total of 3,087 death cases were reviewed from hospital records; a quarter (744/3,087; 24.1%) was BID cases and two third (2,343/3,087; 75.9%) was HAD cases. Mean age was 44 years (SD ± 12). Gastrointestinal and hepatobiliary diseases were the most prevalent cause among all deaths, accounting for half of them (50.5%). The remaining cause of death in order of frequency were as follows: hypertension (37.1%), cardiac diseases (27.4%), hematological diseases (22%),

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tuberculosis (20%), renal diseases (16.2%), malignancy (15%), surgery related death (12.3%), chronic obstructive airway disease (COPD) (11%), HIV infection (10%), stroke (9%), autoimmune diseases (9%), accidents and injury (9%), diabetes mellitus (6%), and poisoning including suicide & homicide (3%). Nearly 85% of cases had more than one disease. Of all deaths, communicable diseases (CDs) attributed 30%; and 46% were due to non-communicable diseases (NCDs).

Among all deaths due to renal diseases, acute kidney injury (AKI) was noted in 10%; chronic kidney disease/end stage renal disease (CKD/ESRD) was seen in 90%. AKI was mainly associated with septicemia and volume loss; septicemia led to septic shock multi-organ failure (acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS), and disseminated intravascular coagulation DIC). Those deaths with CKD/ESRD had co-morbid diseases like hypertension (90%), diabetes mellitus (10%), ischemic heart disease and heart failure (25%), cerebrovascular accidents (10%), COPD (10%), autoimmune diseases (10%) and chronic liver disease with portal hypertension (5%).

Regarding the proportion of BID and HAD cases in renal disease related deaths, only one percent them was BID and almost all (99%) were HAD indicating they received in-patient-care.

Conclusion: Number of death due to non-communicable diseases (NCDs) was higher than that of communicable diseases (NCDs) among working age group in 10 years retrospective study; kidney disease was sixth leading cause of death. Chronic kidney disease/ESRD attributed 90% of kidney disease related deaths and they had associated co-morbid diseases. Hypertension was the most common co-morbid disease. To reduce the kidney disease related morbidity and mortality in working age group, hospital in-patient-care was not adequate. We need to strengthen preventive measures, early detection and treatment of non-communicable diseases (hypertension, diabetes mellitus, CKD), health education and life style modification to delay/prevent the development of CKD. Management of CKD should be placed on the global/national public health agenda.

KEYWORDS: kidney disease, mortality, brought-in-deaths (BID), hospital admission deaths (HAD), working age group, non-communicable diseases (NCDs), communicable diseases (CDs), chronic kidney disease/end stage renal disease (CKD/ESRD)

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INTRODUCTION

Kidney disease has a major impact on global health as its prevalence is increasing. It is a direct cause of global morbidity and mortality worldwide (Bikbov et al., 2020) (Rai et al., 2023) (C. Kovesdy et al., 2006) (Niu et al., 2025). Non-communicable diseases (NCDs), also known as chronic diseases, are characterized by non-contagious nature, multiple risk factors, a long latency period, a prolonged temporal course, functional impairment or disability, and incurability. According to WHO, non-communicable diseases (NCDs) killed at least 43 million people in 2021. In 2021, 18 million people died from an NCDs before age 70 years; 82% of these premature deaths occurred in low- and middle-income countries (WHO, 25 Sept 2025). NCDs were the leading causes of death and disability worldwide. And, WHO stated that 17 million people die from NCDs each year before reaching 70 years of age. Moreover, the majority (86%) of the premature deaths occurring in low- and middle-income countries were reported to be due to NCDs (WHO, 2022).

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is one form of NCDs. Combination of CKD with co-morbid diseases lead to premature death of vascular related diseases like stroke,

ischemic heart diseases and end stage renal disease. Therefore, CKD is a serious public health issue as well as big economic burden. Early screening of risk factors for CKD and co-morbid diseases are extremely important. And they were identified as follows: (1) identify high risk individuals (race, gender, age, and family history like African-American descent, older age, low birth weight and family history of kidney disease); (2) cessation of smoking; (3) prevention of obesity; (4) control of hypertension; (5) control of diabetes mellitus; (6) prevention of exposure to heavy metals; and (7) avoidance of excessive alcohol consumption; (8) cautious use of analgesic; (9) follow up management of those with acute kidney injury; (10) management of those with a history of cardiovascular disease; (11) management of hyperlipidemia; (12) management of metabolic syndrome; (13) management of those with hepatitis C virus; (14) management of those with HIV infection; (15) and management of those with malignancy (Kazancioğlu, 2013) (Romagnani et al., 2017) (Perazella & Khan, 2006).

The kidney is vulnerable to get injury when there is reduction in blood volume, hypersensitivity reaction to drugs, toxins and micro-organism. Acute kidney injury (AKI) was common particularly in those with hypovolemia and sepsis; it caused

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prolonged hospitalization and high mortality (Alayed Tareq et al., 2025) (Walker et al., 2021) (Aukland et al., 2022) (Antonucci et al., 2024).

Mortality included both Brought-in-death (BID) cases and hospital admission deaths. The working age group means those with 18 to 62 years. The mortality related to kidney disease provides valuable insights into the quality of healthcare services, the effectiveness of pre-hospital care, and the prevailing health conditions within the working age group population. Understanding the trends and underlying causes of these deaths is essential for developing kidney targeted interventions and improving overall patient outcomes among the working age group.

METHODS

Study design, Study area and Study period

A hospital based retrospective descriptive study. The design focused on analyzing data from brought-in-deaths (BID) and hospital admission deaths (HAD) among the working age group over a 10-year period (2015-2024). This study was carried out at 1,000 bedded public hospital in Yangon Region which is a large, tertiary care hospital in Yangon, Myanmar. This hospital served a wide catchment area and is a major center for emergency and critical care services. The study period was between January 1, 2015, and December 31, 2024.

Sample size

The sample size included all cases of brought-in-deaths (BID) and hospital admission deaths (HAD) among working age group during the study period. The final number of cases was determined based on hospital records.

Sampling Method and Procedure

A non-probability consecutive sampling method was used. All eligible cases of BID and HAD occurring between 2015 and 2024 were included to ensure comprehensive coverage.

Data collection methods and tools

Procedure

A hospital based retrospective descriptive study was conducted in one selected public hospital in Yangon, Myanmar. The design focused on analyzing data from brought-in-deaths (BID) and hospital admission deaths (HAD) among the working age group (18-62 years) over a 10-year period; January 1, 2015 to December 31, 2024. Brought-In-Death (BID) was defined as a deceased (18-62 years) with no signs of life upon arrival at the hospital and no attempt at resuscitation by medical staff. Hospital Admission Death (HAD) was defined as a patient (18-62 years) who was alive at admission but died during hospitalization, regardless of length of stay. All cases underwent postmortem examination; a forensic medical officer for BID cases and a pathologist for HAD cases. And the cause of death was verified.

Data were extracted retrospectively from the hospital records, including death certificates, admission logs, and diagnostic reports. A standardized form was used to collect demographic details, cause of death, and clinical information. Data were entered into a secured electronic database for analysis.

Inclusion criteria was all BID cases recorded (2015-2024), all HAD cases in working age group within the same period and cases with complete medical records and documented causes of death. The case with incomplete/missing records, case with undocumented or unclear causes and deaths occurring outside the study period (pre-2015, or post-2024) were excluded.

Data management and data analysis

Data were analyzed using SPSS v.23. Descriptive statistics (frequency, means, SDs) summarized the data. Temporal trends were analyzed, subgroup comparisons (age, gender, diagnosis) were performed using chi-square tests, t-tests, or ANOVA. A p -value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Ethical consideration

The study adhered to Declaration of Helsinki. Ethical approval was obtained from the Hospital Ethical Review Committee (ERC) at No. (1) Defense Services General Hospital DSGH (1,000 Bedded), Mingaladon. Patient confidentiality was maintained via anonymizing; no identifiable data were used. As a retrospective study, informed consent was waived; but data were handled with strict confidentiality.

Operational definitions

Brought-In-Death (BID) was defined as a deceased (18-62 years) with no signs of life upon arrival at the hospital and no attempt at resuscitation by medical staff.

Hospital Admission Death (HAD) was defined as a patient (18-62 years) who was alive at admission but died during hospitalization, regardless of length of stay.

Working age group was defined as those with 18 years (completed 18 years at the time of BID or HAD) to 62 years (before completion of 61 years and 12 months at the time of BID or HAD).

'Complete Year of Age' was defined as completed year of age at the time of BID or HAD.

Trends was defined as statistically significant patterns in the frequency, distribution, or characteristics of BID and HAD cases over the study period (2015–2024), analyzed using temporal comparisons.

Cause of death was defined as the primary underlying medical condition, injury, or event documented in official records and postmortem examination (e.g., death certificate or medical officer's report) that directly led to death.

Retrospective study was defined as a study design where pre-existing data (hospital records from 2015–2024) were analyzed to identify associations or trends.

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Acute kidney injury (AKI) was defined as acute rise in serum creatinine with or without oliguria in previously healthy person.

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) was defined as a person with persistent proteinuria over 3 months with or without rise in serum creatinine. According to KDIGO 2012 clinical practice guideline, CKD is classified into the following 6 stages based on the GFR level: (1) Stage 1: Kidney damage with normal GFR (>90 mL/min) but other abnormalities in urine production; (2) Stage 2: Mild reduction in GFR (60-89 mL/min); (3) Stage 3a: Moderate reduction in GFR (45-59 mL/min); (4) Stage 3b: Moderate reduction in GFR (30-44 mL/min); (5) Stage 4: Severe reduction in GFR (15-29 mL/min); and, (6) Stage 5: Renal failure (GFR <15 mL/min). End stage renal disease (ESRD) was defined as the final stage of chronic kidney disease (CKD), defined by a glomerular filtration rate (GFR) of less than 15 mL/min/1.73 m², often necessitating renal replacement therapy such as dialysis or kidney transplantation. a person with very high serum creatinine with GFR less than 10/minutes.

RESULTS

A total of 3,087 cases were reviewed from hospital records. BID cases were nearly a quarter (744/3087, 24.1%); and HAD cases comprised two third (2343/3087, 75.9%) of all deaths. The study population predominantly consisted of male (99.8%) with an average age of 43.5 years (SD ± 11.8). Figure (1) shows distribution of mortality by Disease Category. Gastrointestinal and hepatobiliary diseases were the most prevalent causes of death, accounting for half of them (50.5%). The remaining causes of death in order of frequency were as follows: hypertension (37.1%), cardiac diseases (27.4%), hematological diseases (22%), tuberculosis (20%), renal diseases (16.2%), malignancy (15%), surgery related death (12.3%), COPD (11%), HIV infection (10%), stroke (9%), autoimmune diseases (9%), accidents and injury (9%), diabetes mellitus (6%), and poisoning including suicide & homicide (3%). Eighty-four percent of them had more than one disease; and twenty percent had 4 diseases and above.

Among the deaths due to renal diseases, acute kidney injury (AKI) was noted in 10%; end stage renal disease ESRD was seen in 90%. AKI was mainly associated with septicemia and volume loss; septicemia led to septic shock multi-organ failure (acute respiratory distress syndrome ARDS, and disseminated intravascular coagulation DIC).

Figure (4) shows distribution of co-morbid diseases among renal related deaths (n=501). Those with ESRD had co-morbid diseases like hypertension (90%), diabetes mellitus (10%), ischemic heart disease and heart failure (25%), cerebrovascular accidents (10%), COPD (10%), autoimmune diseases (10%) and chronic liver disease with portal hypertension (5%).

Regarding the proportion of BID and HAD cases in renal diseases, only one percent was BID and almost all (99%) were HAD indicating they received in patient care.

DISCUSSION

This study was done in public hospital handling 1,000 bedded in Yangon, Myanmar. Of 3,087 death cases over 10 years in working age group, BID cases were nearly a quarter; they were mainly due to trauma and accidents. And, HAD cases comprised two third of all deaths.

In this study, death due to communicable diseases (CDs) was 30%; death due to non-communicable diseases (NCDs) was 46%; and, that of accident & poisoning and surgery related was 24%. It showed the burden of NCDs, the “invisible epidemic” that represented the world’s leading cause of death.

WHO stated that cardiovascular diseases accounted for most NCDs deaths, it was followed by cancers, chronic respiratory diseases, and diabetes mellitus (over 2 million including kidney disease deaths caused by diabetes); they caused 80% of all premature NCDs deaths (WHO Sept 25 2025). The burden of NCDs was reported as heavy worldwide (Geng et al., 2025).

Regarding the distribution of mortality by ‘Disease Category’ in this study, gastrointestinal and hepatobiliary diseases were the most prevalent causes of death. They were chronic liver disease, portal hypertension, hepatic encephalopathy, variceal bleeding and chronic liver failure; and 5% of them had CKD/ESRD. Their etiology was alcoholic, hepatitis B and hepatitis C. The remaining causes of death were NCDs; common NCDs in order of frequency in this study were hypertension, cardiac diseases, hematological diseases and renal diseases, malignancy, COPD, stroke, autoimmune diseases and diabetes mellitus.

In this study, although multiple co-morbid diseases were common, death due to renal diseases was sixth leading cause of death in working age group. Therefore, this study pointed out the high burden of renal disease related death even in working age group. And it was comparable with other reports. Claudel et al found that renal disease related mortality was underestimated (Claudel et al., 2023). Chronic renal disease (CKD) and other NCDs are commonly associated; diabetes and hypertension are common etiology of CKD. And their combination cause acceleration of premature atherosclerosis; ischemic heart disease, stroke, heart failure, ESRD and retinopathy.

According to Piovani et al, several factors involved in developing NCDs: modifiable or non-modifiable factors (e.g., age, gender, genetic factors, race, and ethnicity). The modifiable factors were as follows: (1) metabolic/biological (e.g., excess weight/obesity, hyperglycemia, hyperlipidemia, and raised blood pressure); (2) behavioral factors (e.g., unhealthy diet, tobacco use, physical inactivity, and harmful

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use of alcohol or other substances); and (3) societal factors, which involve complex combinations of interacting socioeconomic (e.g., poverty, low public spending on health, limited access to health services); and (4) environmental parameters (e.g., climate change, sunlight, and air pollution) (Piovani et al., 2022). In Myanmar, Htet et al found high prevalences of NCDs risk factors in both urban and rural areas was detected in Myanmar (Htet et al., 2016). Therefore, early detection and management of modifiable factors should be strengthened to reduce morbidity and mortality of CKD.

In this study, the most common co-morbid disease was hypertension; it was recorded in 90% of renal related deaths. Hypertension was found to be etiology of CKD/ESRD as well as complication of CKD/ESRD in this study. The remaining co-morbid diseases were ischemic heart disease, heart failure, COPD, cerebrovascular accidents, auto-immune diseases and diabetes mellitus. Therefore, this finding strongly supported the former reports. CKD cases caused increased all-cause mortality; cardiac death and stroke (Reddan et al., 2003) (Weiner et al., 2004) (Wen et al., 2014) (Ladhani et al., 2017) (Wen et al., 2008) (Jarrar et al., 2025). Both the prevalence of CKD as well as CKD-related mortality were rising both developed and developing countries (Ehtesham et al., 2025a) (C. P. Kovesdy, 2022) (El Nahas & Bello, 2005) (Atkins, 2005) (Chen et al., 2019). Cases with ESRD need renal replacement therapy; hemodialysis, peritoneal dialysis or renal transplant; it gives economic burden worldwide. Moreover, Ali et al reported that the number of deaths among people living with hemodialysis were high; and their cause of death was mainly due to cardiovascular diseases (ALI, 2025). Furthermore, this study period included COVID-19 era, COVID-19 infection in those with CKD caused high morbidity and mortality. In COVID-19 epidemic, increased mortality was found in those with CKD (Pyar et al., 2022) (Pyar et al., 2025). It was in agreement with former reports, Cai et al found that COVID-19 patients with CKD had a high mortality risk requiring a comprehensive multidisciplinary management strategy (Cai et al., 2021). Therefore, having high renal disease related mortality in this study was partly related with SARsCoV2 virus.

In this study, the average age of death was 44 years; the life expectancy in Myanmar was 68.7 years (WHO, 2021). Several findings pointed out that CKD related mortality was common in elderly population ; and, the trend was rising (Ehtesham et al., 2025) (Grobman et al., 2025) (Tang et al., 2024). Nonetheless, CKD related mortality was higher in younger age than that of elderly; Tonelli et al pointed out premature mortality was not uncommon in young adults with CKD (Tonelli et al., 2006). In addition, younger and middle-aged individuals with CKD were at high risk for premature CVD and near-term death (McCullough et al., 2008) (Avorn et al., 2002) (Habib & Saha, 2010). Therefore, this study confirmed the importance of morbidity and mortality of CKD

in working age group. Health screening in younger age group by urinalysis and blood tests is strongly encouraged.

In this study, death due to CDs was 30% and death due to NCDs was 46%. In CD deaths, tuberculosis and HIV infection attributed 30% and 10% respectively. Wagner & Brath pointed out that nearly 80% of NCD deaths occur in low-and middle-income countries (Wagner & Brath, 2012). Non communicable diseases were more and more prevalent in developing countries where they doubled the burden of infective diseases (Boutayeb & Boutayeb, 2005) (Wong et al., 2024). Therefore, prevention and control of not only CDs but also NCDs are important in low resource countries.

In this study, ninety percent of deaths due to renal diseases were due to ESRD; they had co-morbid diseases like hypertension, diabetes mellitus, ischemic heart disease, heart failure, cerebrovascular accidents, COPD and autoimmune diseases. They were common co-morbid diseases reported in other studies. Cardiovascular disease (CVD), CKD, cerebrovascular accidents (CVA) and diabetes were related by sharing etiology and sequalee. CKD caused ischemic heart disease (IHD) by accelerating atherosclerosis and vascular calcification; hence, cardiovascular mortality was increased in patients with CKD/ESRD. Hypercholesterolemia, obesity, hypertension and diabetes mellitus had additive effect on CKD, IHD and stroke (Gimeno-Orna et al., 2015) (Vanholder et al., 2005) (Vanholder et al., 2005) (Mathew et al., 2008) (Rashid et al., 2024). In this study, having non-communicable diseases related deaths in working age group pointed out to reinforce health screening and treatment of modifiable risk factor; obesity, smoking, hypertension, diabetes mellitus and hyperuricemia.

Regarding the proportion of BID and HAD cases in renal disease related deaths, only one percent was BID and almost all (99%) were HAD. It indicated all HAD received in patient care. It clearly demonstrated that not only hospital care but also public health care was required to decrease incidence of kidney diseases, silent invisible epidemic.

In this study, kidney disease related mortality in working age group (18-62 years) was the sixth leading cause of death over 10 years. As of WHO report, the prevalence of NCD were increasing (WHO 2025 Sept). The diseases included in NCD are hypertension, diabetes mellitus, COAD, stroke and malignancy; CKD as a cause of NCD was not frequently mentioned. According to Francis et al, the prevalence of kidney disease was increasing globally and it was the seventh leading risk factor for mortality worldwide (Francis et al., 2024) (Liu et al., 2024) (Neovius et al., 2014). Moreover, nationwide study done in Korea revealed that those with CKD were found to have higher mortality than those without CKD (Kim et al., 2019). Therefore, management of CKD should be intensified to reduce overall mortality.

Furthermore, Shahbazi et al did forecasting global mortality due to CKD; it was expected to increase until 2030. The

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vulnerable group in their study was ‘people with glomerulonephritis, people over 40 years old, and people in high- to middle-income countries’ (Shahbazi et al., 2024). In this study, the youngest was 18 years and the mean age was 44 years. Therefore, health efforts on kidney care should be emphasized at national level; public health care and hospital care including renal replacement therapy. Li et al pointed out to implement a comprehensive strategy to reduce the disease burden of CKD; risk factors prevention at the primary care level; CKD screening among the elderly and high-risk population; and access to high-quality medical services (Li et al., 2023).

Among the deaths due to renal diseases in this study, acute kidney injury (AKI) was noted in 10% of them. They were mainly associated with septicaemia and multi-organ failure like acute respiratory distress syndrome ARDS, septic shock and disseminated intravascular coagulation DIC; therefore, it supported the findings by Abebe et al (Abebe et al., 2021). The various etiology of AKI were hypovolemia, septicemia and toxins/drugs; hence, it was comparable with former reports (Zúñiga-Fernández et al., 2025) (Rout et al., 2024). Moreover, it also pointed out the awareness of AKI in hospitalized patients as it had high mortality; it was previously pointed out by several studies (Abebe et al., 2021) (H. E. Wang et al., 2012) (Pan et al., n.d.) (Alba Schmidt et al., 2024) (Esposito et al., 2025) (Gameiro et al., 2020) (Turgut et al., 2023) (Bagshaw et al., 2010). Furthermore, AKI was associated with not only mortality but also long-term complications like CKD (Ostermann et al., 2025) (Teo et al., 2019) (Tamargo et al., 2024) (Gaut & Liapis, 2021) (Kellum et al., 2021) (Negi et al., 2023) (Pickkers et al., 2021). Gameiro et al reported that the incidence of AKI was increasing; and it was recorded in 15% of hospitalization and half of critically ill patients (Gameiro et al., 2021) (Jamme et al., 2021) (Girling et al., 2020) (Naeem et al., 2025) (Mildh et al., 2016). Therefore, awareness, early intervention and treatment were important to reduce the incidence of AKI and improve the prognosis (Ru et al., 2023) (Coca et al., 2007). Because the causes of AKI were avoidable, preventive measures among the publics as well as health care professionals were essential. Those death due to AKI had comorbidities like hypertension, diabetes, ischemic heart disease; and, they were prone to develop AKI. It was comparable with former reports (Jahantigh et al., 2025) (Coca et al., 2009) (Pfortmueller et al., 2025) (D.-H. Wang et al., 2024). And, treatment of NCDs were important to reduce morbidity and mortality of both AKI and CKD/ESRD.

CONCLUSION

In this retrospective study done over 10 years, the number of deaths among working age group due to non-communicable diseases was higher than that of communicable diseases. Kidney disease related death was sixth leading cause of death.

End stage renal disease (ESRD) was 90% of kidney disease related deaths. To reduce kidney disease related morbidity and mortality in working age group, hospital in patient care only was not adequate. Chronic kidney disease is largely preventable and treatable; it needs greater attention in doing national health policy. We need to encourage preventive measures, early detection and treatment of non-communicable diseases (hypertension, diabetes mellitus, chronic kidney disease), health education and life style modification to delay development of chronic kidney disease/ESRD.

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ETHICAL CONSIDERATION

The data collection using standardized case report forms was approved by Hospital Research and Ethic Committee from No (1) Defense Services General Hospital, Myanmar. Privacy and confidentiality of information were maintained throughout the study process.

DECLARATION OF CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declared no potential conflicts of interests with respect to authorship and publication of this article.

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Kidney Disease Related Death in Working Age Group Over a Ten-Year Period at One Selected Public Hospital in Myanmar: A Retrospective Descriptive Study

Table (1). Age distribution among working age group deaths (n= 3,087)

	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum	N
Complete Year of Age	43.51	10.383	19	62	3,087

Figure (1). Distribution of mortality by Disease Category (n= 3,087)

Figure (2). The proportion of BID cases and HAD cases in each Disease Category (n= 3,087)

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Figure (3). Overall Disease Burden among 'Working age group Deaths' (2015-2024) (n=3,087)

Figure (4). Distribution of co-morbid diseases among renal related deaths (n=501)